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REGIONAL CO-OPERATION (UMISARC) BUILDING
PONDICHERRY UNIVERSITY
PUDUCHERRY, INDIA

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Role of the EU in Development Assistance in Afghanistan Since the fall of Taliban

Nazir Ahmad Yosufi *

Abstract

Today, the European Union (EU) is one of the most important actors in the global aid architecture, both in terms of aid volume and development partnerships. The EU, along with its Member States, is the largest donor of Official Development Assistance (ODA); it provides more than half of the total ODA every year.

After the fall of the Taliban, Afghanistan's stability and development became a priority for the European Union and its Member States. The EU, along its Member States, has committed around over ten billion Euros to Afghanistan since the fall of the Taliban. It has made significant contributions to the diplomatic, military, reconstruction and development of Afghanistan. The EU became the second-largest donor in the areas of humanitarian and economic aid in Afghanistan. However, the EU has been accused of a lack of transparency and giving more off-budget aid to Afghanistan. Therefore, in 2014, it has signed Multilateral Indicative Programme (MIP) during the Karzai government and committed to provide €200 million per year to Afghanistan from 2014-2020 that later in 2016 during the Ashraf Ghani visit to Brussels it increased to €300 million per year.

Thus, the stability in Afghanistan will be beneficial for the European countries, particularly to the EU. First of all, it will stop the influx of Afghan refugees into Europe, and secondly, it will reduce the production and export of Afghan drugs to the European markets. For the reasons mentioned above, the EU signed a State Building Contract with the Afghan government in 2016 for the first time, where €200 million have been directly provided to the Afghan government for two years from 2017 onwards. It will be beneficial for the Afghan government to define its strategic development priorities and domestic policies as outlined in the new Afghanistan National Peace and Development Framework.

Key Words: Development Assistance, Projects, European Union, Afghanistan, Member States.

Overview

Afghanistan is a landlocked country. It has border with six countries such as Pakistan, Iran, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan, Tajikistan, and China. It has been the crossroads of trade, cultures, languages, religions and civilizations (Warikoo, 2002). It is located in the heart of Asia and connects South Asia to the Middle East and Central Asia (Ahmad, 2018, p. 1). Due to its strategic location many empires in the past and many countries today are interested to have presence in Afghanistan. Though, none could stay for a long period of time in Afghanistan that is why it is called the Graveyard of the Empires (Jones, 2010). However, Afghanistan has been receiving foreign assistance for the past several decades (Goodhand, 2002). Since 1960s, many European countries were involved in the reconstruction of Afghanistan. For instance, Germany was the third largest donor to Afghanistan after the Soviet Union and United States (US) during the 1960s and 1970s (Totakhail, 2011). It has completed projects in the areas of healthcare, education, agriculture, geological surveys and trade (Ibid, 2011). France was involved in education sector and built two Franco-Afghan schools in Kabul during the same period.

However, during the cold war, foreign assistance was influenced by the superpowers rivalry; from 1979 to 1989, the Soviet Union directed around \$45 billion to Afghanistan (Runion, 2007). On the other hand, the United States (US) and Saudi Arabia spent \$40 billion in helping the Mujahideen to fight against the Soviets. The foreign development assistance significantly reduced for Afghanistan after the dissolution of the Union of Soviet Socialist Republics (USSR). The proxy war between the Soviet and US for a decade resulted in the destruction of Afghanistan. Further, the 1990s marked as aid fatigue by the donor community due to the fear that foreign aid would generate dependency relationships with the developing countries (Kanbur, 2003, p. 2). As a result, the international community including the EU side-lined Afghanistan during this period and, the latter faced significant political, security, and economic problems which fuelled civil war and emergence of the Taliban in the country for another decade (1990-2000). Even today, Afghanistan is one of the countries that have the largest number of mines in the world despite of the UN Mine Action Services and its efforts since the fall of the Taliban regime (UNMAS Annual Report 2012, p. 11).

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EU's Development Cooperation Policy

The foundation for the European development cooperation was placed at the beginning of the European Economic Community (EEC). The Rome Treaty in 1957 created European Development Fund for the assistance of the European colonies and overseas territories (EC, 2014, p. 3). During the decolonization in 1960s, the Member States (MS) provided aid to their respective colonies following their independence (ibid, 2014). However, the policy gradually stretched to developing countries of Asia, Latin America and European neighbourhood; in 2000 it reached African, Caribbean and Pacific (ASP) countries (ibid, 2014). Today, the EU is one of the most important actors in the global aid architecture both in terms of aid volume and development partnerships. The EU along with its MS is the largest donor of Official Development Assistance (ODA); it contributes more than half of the total ODA every year. The former along its MS contributed fifty-two per cent of total global ODA in 2013, and more than two-thirds of total aid was in the form of grants.

Figure 1: Net ODA in 2016 - as a percentage of GNI

Source: Development Cooperation Report, 2017, p. 141

Figure 2: Net ODA volume from DAC Donors in 2016

Source: Development Cooperation Report, 2017, p. 141

In 2016, the total amount of ODA reached to \$142.62 billion which shows around nine per cent increase as compared to 2015 (Development Cooperation Report, 2017, 141). However, the increase was due to the impact of refugee costs in several countries such as Austria, Germany, and Switzerland (ibid, p. 140).

Today, the EU is present in 140 countries with wide-range of sectors (EC, 2014). It has been the leading supporter of the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) for the reduction of poverty in the world and now committed to the implementation of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Further, the Treaty of Lisbon stipulated that the reduction and extermination of poverty are the main objectives of Development Cooperation Policy of the EU (EC, 2014). The EU also provides expertise in the area of human rights, electoral observation, governance, and crisis resolution. The EU along its member states is the largest donor of humanitarian aid in the world; it provides life saving assistance to refugees, internally displaced persons, the victims of disasters, etc. It also works closely with major UN bodies and humanitarian relief agencies. Similarly, the EU is working with over two hundred NGOs that deliver humanitarian aid to the needy regions.

European Union's Role in Afghanistan during the Civil War and the Taliban Regime

The EU was providing assistance to the Afghan people throughout the civil war as well as during the Taliban regime. For instance, the European Civil Protection and Humanitarian Aid Operations (ECHO) directed \$831 million to Afghanistan during the civil war from 1992-1996 (Totakhail, 2011, p. 45). The aid provided for emergency services are food assistance, water and sanitation, health, shelter, protection and education to most vulnerable and conflict affected areas in Afghanistan (Ibid, 2011). 1996 onwards, it was difficult for many international NGOs to operate in Afghanistan due to the harsh regime of the Taliban. Still, the EU provided \$864 million to Afghanistan between 1996 to 2000 (Ibid, 2011). And around 25000 Afghans were employed with the European aid agencies in Afghanistan, for example, the Swedish Committee was the single largest employer in Afghanistan (Goodhand, 2002).

Since the 1990s, Finland has been funding demining efforts through both the UN Mine Action Service (UNMAS) and HALO Trust (Pasternak, 2012). Switzerland also was present in Afghanistan from 1987, and the International Committee of the Red Cross (ICRC) supported the victims of war and agricultural projects in Afghanistan at the time of civil war and the Taliban regime (ICRC Annual Report, 2013). Similarly, Sweden has been active in Afghanistan for the past 35 years. Before the defeat of the Taliban in 2001, the Swedish Committee for Afghanistan (SCA) had more than 39000 girls enrolled in schools in Afghanistan. In fact, the SCA was acting as a Ministry of Education and Health in the country during the Taliban regime (Fänge, 2016). Currently, it has more than 5000 employees in Afghanistan (Swedish Committee for Afghanistan, 2018). Around 70, 000 children go to schools and more than two million people receive medical care yearly at clinics and hospitals that are run by the SCA (Ibid, 2018). It also supports the people with disabilities (ibid 2018).

9/11 Attacks and the EU's Response

During 1995, Professor Barnett R. Rubin predicted that, if the international Community side-line Afghanistan, it would make the world insecure for all (Upadhyay, 2011, p. vii). Though, the United Nations (UN) imposed sanctions on the Taliban in 1999 for the continuous opium production and human rights violations in Afghanistan. Similarly, in December 2000 the UN imposed new sanctions on the Taliban for not handing over Osama Bin Laden (leader of Al Qaeda) to the US. However, it did not change the Taliban's behaviour. It is fair to say that the international community ignored the rebuilding of Afghanistan since the disintegration of Soviet Union until 9/11 happened. Therefore, after 9/11 attacks, the EU fully backed the then US President George Bush's decision on 'War on Terror'. The United Nation Security Council (UNSC) permitted the use of all necessary steps to respond to the Al Qaeda attacks. Thereafter, with the Europeans full support the US began the 'war on terror' in Afghanistan and toppled the Taliban regime in 2001. Since then, Afghanistan once again became the centre of attraction for the international community,

particularly to the EU. After 9/11, the EU's specific attention is to the most vulnerable countries and around half its development aid goes to the fragile states for peace building and state building (EC, 2014).

European Union's Role in Afghanistan after the Taliban Regime

After fall of the Taliban Regime in 2001, Afghanistan's stability and development became priority for the EU and MS. The EU committed to pursue multilateral solutions to the war in Afghanistan through mediation, conferences and negotiations for the greater goal of supporting institution building and good-governance during and post conflict reconstruction process. The formal process and international efforts led by the EU and sponsored by the UN were started at the Bonn conference in November 2001 where some Afghan groups of different ethnicity were also present. The different groups at the conference agreed to create a temporary transitional government and more importantly the establishment of a process for the political, economic and social reconstruction of a war-damaged country. As a result, Hamid Karzai selected as the Afghan Interim Authority (AIA) and subsequently elected as the Afghanistan president in 2004. It is worth mentioning that the EU was very successful in bringing all factions of Afghans on a single table and created a relatively peaceful environment in Afghanistan.

After the Bonn conference, on December 10, 2001, the EU appointed Mr Klaiber as the EU Special Representative (EUSR) to Afghanistan and contributed to the integrity and full implementation of EU-Afghanistan Joint Declaration (Yearbook of European Security, 2013). And some prominent European countries took leading role in different sectors in Afghanistan, for instance, the United Kingdom (UK) took the lead for fighting narcotics; Italy reforming the judicial sector; Germany training the Afghan National Police (ANP); the European Commission took the leading role for rural livelihoods and health and France as coordinator for the establishment of the Afghan Parliament (EU Council Secretariat Factsheet, 2005). In 2007, the EU also started a police mission 'EUPOL 2007' in Afghanistan under the European Security and Defence Policy (ESDP) to train and reform Afghan National Police (EU, 2010). And it also took the responsibility to reinforce democracy, governance, the rule of law, agriculture, rural development and the healthcare system in Afghanistan (European Union External Action, 2016).

The remaining individual MS contributed large number of troops to the International Security Assistance Forces (ISAF) mission in Afghanistan from 2002 to 2014. The EU along its Member States has committed to allocate around €8 billion (over \$10 billion) to Afghanistan from 2002-2010 (Buckley, 2010).

Table 1: The EU/European Countries Aid to Afghanistan from 2002-2010 (in \$ million)

Donor Countries/ Institutions	Commitments	Disbursements
European Union and European Commission	2,883	2,594
United Kingdom	2,222	2,222
Netherlands	1,015	1,015
Germany	2,130	762
Sweden	635	635
Italy	645	540
Denmark	438	438
Spain	220	194
France	323	174
Finland	160	160
Total	10,671	8,734

Source: Bizhan, 2018, p. 84-85

As seen in table 1, the EU and its MS has committed to provide over \$10 billion to Afghanistan from 2002 to 2010. However, at the end of 2010 it has disbursed \$8,734 million (Bizhan, 2018). There is a difference of almost \$2 billion between the commitment and the disbursement of assistance to Afghanistan (ibid 2018). However, numerous projects had been affected due to shortage of timely funds during the aforementioned period in Afghanistan. Professor Buckley in her paper argues that the EU set a poor example to others because its institutions and MS do not coordinate properly (Buckley, 2010, p. 2).

Table 2: EU Development Assistance to Afghanistan 2002- 2016 (in € million)

Year	Commitments	Disbursements	Year	Commitments	Disbursements
2002	247.59	151.04	2010	254.61	215.20
2003	285.55	213.90	2011	347.00	261.41
2004	247.55	171.19	2012	283.61	199.63
2005	224.48	206.11	2013	316.86	188.41
2006	200.53	175.98	2014	297.90	270.50
2007	195.90	224.59	2015	275.00	173.00
2008	214.49	213.27	2016	362.00	268.00
2009	269.83	285.65	Total	4.022.90	3.217.88

Source: European Union External Action, 2017, p. 5

As seen in the Table 2, the EU alone has committed €4 billion to Afghanistan from 2002 to 2016. However, according to the EU's data the actual aid disbursement to Afghanistan during mentioned period was 25 per cent less than the commitments. On top of that, according to the studies around seventy per cent of actual disbursement was in the form of off budget.

Criticism about EU's Development Assistance in Afghanistan

In 2011, an Afghan Member of Parliament, Golalei Nur accused the EU for not properly managing its aid in Afghanistan (Gaylord, 2011). She also said, that there is a "serious" lack of transparency in the way the aid is spent in the country (ibid 2011). According to Dr Bizhan study in 2018, around 70 per cent of the aid provided by the EU and European Commission to Afghanistan were off budget (Bizhan, 2018). In addition, the MS emphasize more on national involvement and national profile in Afghanistan instead of global EU efforts (Stockli, 2014, p.8).

Professor Joanna Bukley in her paper argue that the EU is not making impact in Afghanistan that matches its financial, civilian and military assistance to the country. It is too poorly organised to capitalise fully on its strengths as a multilateral organization, and its member-states lack a clear vision of the role they want the European institutions to play (Bukley, 2010, p. 1).

However, around 70 per cent of the European development assistance that provided to Afghanistan from 2002 bypassed the government institutions. According to the economists, the Afghan government lost its credibility in the eyes of its citizens because the donor countries bypassed the government. For the maximisation of the assistance impact, the EU focused on cooperation mechanism among the European donors. For instance, the EU developed the Overseas Development Policy to resolve the assistance problems, as Member States developed conflict over the assistance areas, such as Germany interested in one country and France in the other. Therefore, the EU decided to focus on the issues rather than the areas, for example, poverty, health, education, etc.

In the EU-Afghanistan Country Strategy Paper, the resources focused on six areas of cooperation, where three areas are priorities or focal areas such as governance, rural development and health and three of which are non-focal areas such as social protection (refugees/returnees), de-mining and regional cooperation (European Commission, 2013).

Specifically, the EU signed Multi-Annual Indicative Programme (MIP) during the Karzai government in 2014 (EEAS, 2014). The EU will provide a total of €1.4 billion for the period between 2014-2020 to Afghanistan through this instrument (EEAS and EU, 2014). The money will allocate to various sectors such as agriculture, health, policing and rule of law, and democratisation and accountability, 30, 25, 29, and 15 per cent respectively (ibid, 2014). For further details, see the below table.

Table 3: Tentative Timetable of EU's Funds Commitment to Afghanistan (2014 to 2020)

Sectors	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	Total
1) Agriculture & Rural Development	102.5	-	80	-	70	-	84.5	337
2) Health	37	43	-	100	-	94	-	274
3) Policing and Rule of Law	-	91	30	-	60	60	78	319
4) Democratisation & Accountability	40	-	20	30	-	45	28	163
5) Incentive	23	67	70	70	70	-	-	300
Support measures	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	7
Total Commitments	203.5	202	201	201	201	200	191.5	1400

Source: EEAS and EC, 2014, p. 25

In 2014, the EU also included Afghanistan under its Generalized Scheme of Preferences (GSP), called 'Everything but Arms (EBA)' through which Afghanistan can export anything to the EU without duty/tariffs but except arms, ammunition, and sugar (Schueren and Layton, 2014, p. 1). These initiatives confirm the EU's long-term engagement in support of the Afghanistan government's strategies for the development and economic growth.

Role of the EU in Afghanistan after 2014

President Ashraf Ghani resumed office at the end of 2014 when the country was in a bad situation in terms of security particularly economy. Due to the following factors, the country was facing severe economic problems: (1) withdrawal of international forces; (2) large number of NGOs closed their offices in different parts of the country (resulted in all time high unemployment rate); (3) Reduction of development assistance to Afghanistan; (4) the emergence of Islamic State (Daesh); (5) Taliban refusal of peace talks with the National Unity Government and finally, for the first time, Taliban took over the control of Kunduz province in 2015. The civilian casualties increased around 20 per cent in 2014 and further 10 per cent increased in 2015 (UNAMA Report, 2018). On top of that, the EU's role in Afghanistan became shallow from 2014 till 2016. As a result, most of the businessmen transferred their money/businesses to other countries such as Dubai, Pakistan, Iran etc. during this period.

European Reaction towards Afghan Refugees

2015 onwards, the Afghan people lost their hope in the government, international community as well as in the EU for bringing peace in Afghanistan. As a result, millions of people displaced within the country and some started moving to the neighbouring or to other the countries (Stanzel, 2016). However, after Angela Merkel (German Chancellor), announcement of 'Wir Schafen Das!' (We can do it!) Lots of Afghans moved from neighbouring countries towards European countries, mainly to Germany. At the end of 2015, the number of Afghan refugees applied for the asylum

At the end of 2015, the number of Afghan refugees applied for the asylum in Europe reached 180,000 that formed the second highest number of refugees after the Syrians (Ibid 2016).

In 2016, most of the European countries reacted to the influx of Refugees and termed it as the Refugee Crisis in Europe. In order to reduce the number of Afghan refugees in Europe particularly in Germany the Embassy of German in Kabul initiated a campaign through media (social, print, audio and video media) to discourage the Afghan migration to the European countries. However, it did not stop them (Stanzel, 2016). According to the surveys, more than 70 per cent of Afghans have fear of personal safety. In this regard, the EU invited President Ashraf Ghani to Brussels on October 2, 2016 to discuss the Afghan refugee issue. They asked the Afghan government to find the root causes of migration and to improve the country's migration management system. After the discussion, an agreement was signed titled as Joint Way Forward on Migration Issues between both parties for cooperation on the return and readmission of irregular Afghan migrants. For the first time, the EU signed a State Building Contract with the Afghan government in 2016 and committed to provide €200 million directly to the Afghan government for two years from 2017 onwards (EC, 2016, p.1).

Two days later, the EU hosted an international conference on Afghanistan in Brussels. The international donors committed \$15.2 billion to Afghanistan for the period 2016-2020 (EC, 2016, p. 29). Interestingly, the EU along its MS contributed \$5.6 billion from the total assistance to Afghanistan (ibid, 2016). Further, the 2014 MIP agreement which was signed during Karzai government has been increased from €200 to €300 million per year to Afghanistan from 2016-2020 during Ashraf Ghani Brussels visit in 2016 (ibid 2016). These initiatives were good steps toward strengthening the Afghan government which will be beneficial for the Afghan government to define its domestic policies and strategic development priorities that are outlined in the new Afghanistan National Peace and Development Framework (ANPDF). The Commissioner for International Development, Mr. Neven Mimica, said, "Now is not the time to reduce our ambition or our investment in the people of Afghanistan" (BBC News, 2016).

Furthermore, the EU and Afghan government signed another Cooperation Agreement on Partnership and Development (CAPD) in 2017 (EUEA, 2017). This new mutually benefited framework emphasized on wide range of areas. It includes economy, politics, the rule of law, health and rural development, education, science and technology, and actions to fight corruption, money laundering, terrorist financing, organized crime and narcotics (ibid, 2017). It also foresees cooperation on migration that is based on the Joint Forward on Refugees/migration issues that adopted on 2nd October 2016 (ibid, 2017). In 2018, the European Commission committed to provide €37.5 million to the people affected by natural disasters and conflict in Afghanistan, Iran and Pakistan. It will cover emergency care, food, water and sanitation, shelter and protection to newly displaced persons (EC, 2018). Through this agreement, Iran will get €5 million and Pakistan will get €5.5million to support the Afghan refugees and provide them food, shelter, health, protection, as well as education to the vulnerable Afghan children (EC, 2018).

On February 8, 2018 the EU took a step further by launching the Joint EU-Afghanistan Committee. It is a new level of cooperation and partnership that trying to reinforce security, good governance, economic growth and human rights (EEAS, 2018). The Joint Committee first meeting held at Brussels under the EU-Afghanistan Cooperation Agreement on Partnership and Development (CAPD) and discussed the reform agenda that agreed at Brussels Conference on Afghanistan in 2016. Federica Mogherini and Eklil Hakimi reiterated their mutual and strong commitment for bringing peace and stability to the Afghan people and emphasised on reconciliation, regional cooperation, and sustainable development with real benefits to the people of Afghanistan. In this context, the EU is trying to be strong, reliable and important partner for Afghans and will work to uplift the lives of the Afghan people (Ibid, 2018). The EU's main investments will be focused on the sectors such as education, health, human development, democracy and security, with the aim to lessen poverty in Afghanistan. Currently, Afghanistan is one of the poorest countries in the world and according to the Central Statistics Organization and ICON International, 54 per cent of Afghanistan's population living below poverty line (BPL) (ToloNews, 2018). The EU wishes to focus on the common efforts such as combating

corruption, supporting refugees and refugees/migrants. It stressed on timely parliamentary elections and now supports the Afghan presidential election as soon as possible (ibid, 2018). Finally, the EU realized that the stability in Afghanistan would be beneficial for the European countries too.

Problem of Narcotic production

After the Bonn conference in 2001, the UK took the leading role in fighting the production of narcotics in Afghanistan (Mansfield, 2017). The UK choose Helmand province which is number one opium producer in Afghanistan (ibid 2017). Initially, the UK initiated an important counter narcotics and economic development programme in Helmand which was encouraged by the partner countries. At the beginning, the UK was successful in fighting narcotics, for example, removed Sher Mohd Akhundzada (Governor of Helmand province) in 2005 as he caught with nine tonnes of opium at his residence (Suhrke, 2011). However, Lieutenant Colonel Tootal during his visit in 2006 explicitly said to the people that his troops would not eradicate the poppy farms and added that there is a lack of resources to address the issue of counter narcotics (Ibid). Since then, the cultivation increased many folds not only in Helmand province but all over the country. According to the SIGAR reports, billions of dollars have been spent for counter narcotics efforts, since 2002, in Afghanistan (SIGAR Report, 2018). Despite of these efforts the opium production reached an all-time high in 2017. According to the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC) report of 2017, the poppy cultivation increased by 63% and production by 87% as compare to the previous year (UNODC Report, 2017). Around 60 per cent of the opium cultivation took place in the Southern region of the country (UNODC, 2017). The production reached 9000 tonnes from 4800 tonnes in 2016 (Ibid 2017).

Figure 3: Afghan Opium Cultivation, Eradication, and Production since 2008

Source: SIGAR Report, 2018

The figure shows that the opium production increased every year. Currently, Afghanistan is producing 80% of the world’s opium (SIGAR, 2018). The opium economy is ten times more than the formal economy of Afghanistan. After a decade of counter-narcotics efforts by the international community that could not reduce the production of opium. Thus, the Afghan government want to formalize the opium sector in order to reduce the aid dependency but rejected by the international community.

Afghanistan is an agrarian country where most of its revenues come from agricultural activities. Although, during Taliban rule most of the revenues were coming from opium production. After the fall of Taliban regime, the Afghan government announced the production of opium illegal in the country with the hope that the in international community will help the people in replacing the opium production with the alternative sources. However, the production of opium under the Taliban regime in 2001 was 185 tonnes (UNDCP Annual Survey, 2001, iii) Today, it is more than

9000 tonnes per year which means it increased around 50 times (UNODC, 2017). Afghanistan becomes the largest exporter of opium to the world particularly to European markets (UNODC, 2017). After a decade of failure in fighting opium production in the country, the Afghan government proposed international community to formalize it. However, the international community is neither helping to remove it nor want it to be in the formal sector.

Conclusion

The EU was involved in Afghanistan decades before the war on terror. It was helping the Afghan people throughout the civil war as well as during the Taliban regime whereas many European countries were actively supporting Afghanistan via Pakistan at the time of the Taliban rule. The EU was the main supporter of the Afghan refugees in the world particularly in Iran and Pakistan.

However, after fall of the Taliban regime there has been watershed in aid commitment to Afghanistan by the EU. The latter, put lots of efforts and also invested billions of Euros for the development, economic recovery, fighting narcotics, bringing peace and stability in Afghanistan. The EU became the second largest humanitarian and economic donor to Afghanistan. It supported the return of Afghan refugees to their country from different parts of the world, especially, from Pakistan and Iran. Though, there is security problem in the country but it has improved a lot in different sectors as compare to the Taliban era. The Afghan people have been very grateful to the EU and European countries for their continuous assistance and support. The EU's aid to Afghanistan has been relatively more of on budget and transparent as compare to the US. The Afghan people view the European presence positively in Afghanistan except the United Kingdom.

Afghanistan remained one of the poorest country in the world with more than 57 per cent of the Afghan population living below poverty line despite of generous development aid from the EU and MS in the areas of humanitarian and economic to Afghanistan since 2002. Since fall of the Taliban, the production of opium increased around 50 times (185 tonnes in 2001 and now more than 9000 tonnes per year). In 2018, Afghanistan ranked fourth most corrupt nation in the world by the Corruption Perception Index. Insecurity is increasing day by day and the Taliban are controlling more than half of the national territory. It indicates that, what has been done in Afghanistan by the EU and MS has been ineffective. Since 2001, the EU and MS also committed mistakes in Afghanistan. For instance, (i) the EU along others from the beginning ignored the Afghan government and created a parallel public sector which undermined the Afghan government accountability and credibility in the eyes of its citizens. (ii) 2001 onwards, whatever (Weapons, Water or Cosmetics) NATO, EU etc. imported into Afghanistan did not paid taxes to the Afghan government which further created a window of corruption for other national and international companies to import without providing tax to the government. However, Today Afghanistan needs the EU more than any other time to support her. The EU with the support of international community could put pressure on Pakistan for cooperation with Afghanistan. The stability in Afghanistan will result in eradication of opium production and reduction in influx of Afghan refugee into Europe. Overall, the stability in Afghanistan will be beneficial to the European countries.

Endnotes

- i Fighters who fought against the Soviet Union invasion in Afghanistan from 1979-89
- ii Terrorist organization.

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